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Coupling of a 3D Ecosystem Model with HYCOM

by

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Abstract

The Ocean Global Circulation Models (OGCMs) aim at simulating the various movements of the ocean, one of them being the Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model (MICOM) developed at the Rosenstiel School of Marine and Atmospheric Sciences at the University of Miami and used at the NERSC. A more recent model, HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model (HYCOM), which actually derivate from MICOM and is in its basis isopycnal too, has also been used at the NERSC. While MICOM has already been coupled to an Ecosystem Model to simulate movements and behaviour of biological tracers, this has not been the case for HYCOM yet. Therefore I was entrusted to implement an ecosystem model with the HYCOM code.

The first two chapters of this report consist of a brief theoretical presentation of respectively the physical and the ecosystem models, the purpose being to report the bibliography study I did before starting practicing. It should set the context of the project. Then, in the third chapter, the different steps for dealing with the project and some problems encountered are described, and eventually an outcome of this training period is built. Finally, the last chapter discusses some of the results that were obtained and that are presented here as well.

Chapter 1

The Physical Model

In this chapter, MICOM and HYCOM models are presented in a rather succinct way; since HYCOM derives from MICOM, the background is the same for both models. Indeed, that they solve the same equations, are both isopycnic models in the deep ocean and use both a split-explicit scheme. However, they are different in other aspects: the vertical discretization differs in the top of the ocean, and the vertical mixing processes are not computed similarly.

This part should give an overview of the theoretical basis of the models, of the numerical issues, and help the reader defining the important issues related to the coupling of an ecosystem model with HYCOM instead of MICOM, which has already been done. Actually it is a reformulation of the bibliography study I have done, using my own words, trying to write something I would have liked to read when I started the training period and that would have quickly provided me with a general view of the models.

1.1 Discretization

Before solving equations and modeling the ocean and its movements, one has to discretize the model domain on its whole depth (from the bottom floor to the surface), and to define an horizontal grid. This is what this section deals with.

1.1.1 Different types of vertical discretization

There are a few ways of discretizing the ocean in the vertical, and here is a short presentation of z -, σ -, and of isopycnic coordinate models.

- z -coordinate models

In these models, the ocean is divided in the vertical into levels of constant depth. It is the most obvious model and the simplest too, so it was mainly used when the first models were implemented a couple of decades ago. To improve it, one can define thinner layers close to the surface (in this case it is not a uniform discretization anymore). This type of discretization is used in the Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory (GFDL), model originally developed by (Bryan, 1969) and (Cox & Bryan, 1984), and in the closely related Modular Ocean

general circulation Model (MOM) (Pinardi and Navarra, 1993; Roussenov *et al*; Wu and Haines, 1996).

- **σ -coordinate models**

In these models the coordinate $\sigma = \frac{z-\zeta}{H+\zeta}$ remains constant for a given coordinate surface. ζ stands for the sea level elevation, H is the total ocean depth and z is the depth.

With this definition of the vertical coordinate system, the vertical resolution increases naturally in shallow-water. This discretization is used in the Princeton Ocean General Circulation Model (POM) developed by (Blumberg & Mellor, 1987).

- **isopycnic coordinate models**

The density is used for discretizing in the vertical so that the ocean is splitted into layers with constant density. Thus the model consists of a stack of layers, being modeled by a set of shallow-water equations, and the interaction between the layers will mainly be through hydrostatic pressure forces.

1.1.2 Vertical discretization in MICOM: an isopycnic model

The Miami Isopycnic Coordinate Ocean Model is a three dimensional isopycnic coordinate model of the stratified ocean interior and consists of a number of layers of constant density. On top of them, the model includes a single-layer, a bulk mixed layer, which is non isopycnal and is driven by conventional atmospherical forcing fields. A clear distinction is drawn between the mixed layer and the interior water and this will be discussed further in section 1.3.3

1.1.3 Why using isopycnic models?

Within the ocean, the mixing processes take place mainly along surfaces of constant density. To be more precise, the cross-isopycnal mixing (mixing in the diapycnal direction) is order of magnitudes less than the mixing along density surfaces. This fact makes the oceanographers work with isopycnic models. Moreover, these models have several advantages. Other models such as z -coordinates or σ -coordinate models introduce numerical errors while modeling diapycnal mixing, and these are physical errors. Indeed, z - or σ -coordinate models introduce artificial mixing whenever an isopycnal surface crosses a model coordinate surface. This artificial mixing will be directed along isopycnals in an isopycnic ocean model. Thus, the artificial numerical mixing in an isopycnic model is hidden behind the strong physical mixing acting along isopycnals in the ocean.

Only two dimensional equations have to be solved so there is no numerical smoothing of the dynamic field in the diapycnal direction.

Level or sigma coordinate models require very high vertical resolution to solve the moving pycnocline while an isopycnic model will always have the resolution where there are changes in density.

An isopycnic model can resolve baroclinic systems with considerably fewer grid levels

than z -coordinate models.

One can also add that in level models the observed bathymetry has to be transformed into a discrete set of depths in contrast to the isopycnic model which can cope with any depth.

However, isopycnic models actually deal with potential density, i.e. that the density is calculated with the pressure fixed at the surface pressure value. This generates some problems: for instance Antarctic bottom water becomes lighter than the South Atlantic bottom water which is definitely not the case in reality. And if one tries to solve the problem with using pressure at 2000m as potential pressure, it gives birth to incoherences in the surface circulation, at high latitudes.

1.1.4 Vertical discretization in HYCOM

The HYbrid Coordinate Ocean Model, is a hybrid coordinate model. Indeed, it is isopycnal in the open, stratified ocean and it uses z -level coordinates in the mixed layer. The theoretical foundation for implementing such a coordinate was set forth in Bleck and Boundra (1981) and (Bleck & Benjamin, 1993).

As seen it on figure 1.1, to each level-coordinate surface of the upper part of the

Figure 1.1: Vertical discretization in HYCOM

ocean corresponds a reference isopycnal: in the mixed layer, grid points are placed vertically so that a smooth transition of each layer interface from an isopycnic to a constant-depth surface occurs whenever it enters the mixed layer.

HYCOM has the advantages of isopycnic models given in section 1.1.3; moreover, it extends the geographic range of applicability of traditional isopycnic coordinate circulation models such as MICOM toward unstratified part of the ocean. It allows a high vertical resolution in the surface mixed layer for proper representation of thermodynamical and biochemical processes.

1.1.5 Horizontal grid

The equations are formulated on the Mercator grid shown in figure 1.2. It has 70 points in i-direction and 65 points in j-direction, and has a higher resolution in the Northern Atlantic part.

1.2 Equations solved in MICOM and HYCOM

Here is a presentation of the equations that are dealt with in MICOM and HYCOM. In classical fluid dynamics, to build a complete set of equations, one must take into account the continuity equation, the momentum equation for the velocity vector, the energy conservation equation, the boundary and initial conditions, and an equation of state. Since we are dealing with the ocean, we must also take into account salinity, with another conservation equation.

1.2.1 Continuity equation

The continuity equation for layer thickness, $\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha}$, is given by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right) + \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\vec{v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\alpha \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right) = 0. \quad (1.1)$$

Here, \vec{v} is the horizontal velocity vector, p is the pressure and $\alpha = \rho^{-1}$ is the specific volume.

1.2.2 Momentum equation for the velocity vector

The 2-dimensional part of this equation reads:

$$\frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial t_\alpha} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla_\alpha \vec{v} + f \vec{k} \wedge \vec{v} + \left(\alpha \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right) \frac{\partial \vec{v}}{\partial p} + \nabla_\alpha M = -g \frac{\partial \vec{\tau}}{\partial p} + \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \right)^{-1} \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\mu \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \nabla_\alpha \vec{v} \right). \quad (1.2)$$

Here, \vec{k} is a vertical unit vector, μ is a variable eddy coefficient, $\vec{\tau}$ is the wind- and bottom-drag-induced shear stress vector and $M = gz + p\alpha$ is the Montgomery potential. The 3rd dimension part of this equation reads:

$$\frac{\partial M}{\partial \alpha} = p. \quad (1.3)$$

This equation is obtained under the hydrostatic assumption.

1.2.3 Energy conservation

Actually, we use the heat conservation equation

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} T \right) + \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\vec{v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} T \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\alpha \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} T \right) = \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\mu \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \nabla_\alpha T \right) + \mathcal{H}_T. \quad (1.4)$$

Here, T is the temperature and \mathcal{H}_T represents the sum of the diabatic source terms acting on T .

Figure 1.2: Horizontal grid

1.2.4 Salinity conservation

The salinity conservation equation reads

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_\alpha} \left(\frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} S \right) + \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\vec{v} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} S \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} \left(\alpha \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} S \right) = \nabla_\alpha \cdot \left(\mu \frac{\partial p}{\partial \alpha} \nabla_\alpha S \right) + \mathcal{H}_S. \quad (1.5)$$

Here, S is the salinity and \mathcal{H}_S represents the sum of the diabatic source acting on S .

1.2.5 Equation of state

Finally, we have the equation of state which gives the relation between the density σ and the temperature and salinity. This relation is approximated as described below according to the Knudsen Formula by (Friedrich & Levitus, 1972),

$$\sigma(T, S) = c_1 + c_2 T + c_3 S + c_4 T^2 + c_5 S T + c_6 T^3 + c_7 S T^2, \quad (1.6)$$

where the constant c_N depend on the depth z according to

$$c_N = \alpha_N + \beta_N z + \gamma_N z^2, \quad (1.7)$$

with α_N , β_N and γ_N empirical constants, see (Friedrich & Levitus, 1972)

1.3 Implementation

After setting the equations and the way of discretizing the ocean, this section roughly presents the implementation in MICOM and HYCOM.

1.3.1 Split-explicit scheme

In both MICOM and HYCOM, a split explicit scheme is used. Indeed, within the ocean, velocities of waves' propagation vary on a wide range of time scales: actually, external gravity waves can propagate with velocities of up to hundreds of meters per second whereas internal waves have velocities on the order of 1 meter per second or even less. Now let us consider for instance an explicit scheme for the discretization: the time step, above which the numerical scheme becomes unstable, must be much smaller when the external gravity waves are included, than if only the internal waves were present. To improve this, an alternative is to split the equations into two systems that model the fast motions (barotropic system) and the slow motions (baroclinic system) separately. So the numerical cost of carrying the fast waves will be reduced. The baroclinic system is fully 3D, while the barotropic system is 2D since fast motions are approximately independent of z .

So we decompose the velocity components into barotropic and baroclinic components:

$$u = \bar{u} + u' \quad \text{and} \quad v = \bar{v} + v', \quad (1.8)$$

and the pressure field is decomposed as

$$p = p'(1 + \eta), \quad (1.9)$$

where p' is the baroclinic pressure component and η is the barotropic pressure component. We have $\eta \ll 1$ thus $(1 + \eta)$ is approximated by 1 where it appears as a factor.

The continuity and the momentum equations are discretized according to this splitting (See appendix A).

The barotropic equations are solved using a forward-backward scheme and the baroclinic momentum equation is integrated following a Leapfrog scheme.

The barotropic equations are integrated with a time step approximately 1/12 of the time step for the baroclinic equations.

1.3.2 Isopycnal outcropping

The layer outcropping problem is considered to many as the number one problem in isopycnic modeling. Indeed, dynamics may bring some layers to disappear, some to appear, and not all isopycnic layers can be expected to exist everywhere in the computational domain. Thus advanced positive definite numerical advection routines consider that each isopycnic layer exist everywhere but is allowed to become massless. Actually the model equations rule when and where a layer will vanish or on the contrary start filling up with water (for instance water will outcrop to the mixed layer or to the bottom) and special algorithms maintain positive definiteness of layer thicknesses.

1.3.3 Vertical mixing

In the ocean surface boundary layer, the atmospheric conditions provide a kinetic energy which, by compensating the potential energy, leads to an unstable state. Wind stress and cooling of the surface water create turbulence in this surface boundary layer, while viscous dissipation and heating tend to suppress it. So two distinct regimes of oceanic vertical mixing are identified: ocean mixing in the boundary layer near the surface (Mixed Layer) under a variety of surface forcing conditions such as the wind stress, and ocean mixing in the ocean interior due to internal waves, shear instability and double diffusion.

Vertical mixing and the Kraus-Turner scheme in MICOM

Four different vertical mixing processes are considered, i.e. mixed layer entrainment and detrainment, convection, and diapycnal mixing.

- Convection

The algorithm used for the convection is rather simple: it considers the density of the mixed layer, and if this density is higher than the density in the next layer, the situation has to be stabilized, which is done by mixing the two layers. Then the new mixed layer depth is the sum of the two layers while the layer k vanished. Heat and salt conservations provide new temperature and salinity for the mixed layer while the momentum is conserved by integrating it over the new surface layer.

Then the process goes on until the situation is stable, i.e. until the mixed layer density is lower than the density of the layers below. Note that a higher density in the mixed layer happens for instance when there is enough evaporation.

- Diapycnal mixing

Diapycnal mixing is computed according to the diapycnal turbulent heat and salt fluxes, and is located on the layer interfaces. It's based on the scheme developed by (McDougall & Dewar, 1998)

- Mixed layer

The Kraus-Turner scheme modelise the surface boundary layer by computing a mixed layer that is the uppermost layer; depth of the mixed layer is diagnosed from the turbulence kinetic energy equation. Variables of the mixed layer such as T , S , u , v are averaged along the bulk mixed layer and salinity and temperature are considered homogeneous along the mixed layer. Actually MICOM uses an integral-type model whose development was initiated by (Kraus & Turner, 1967) .

Depending on the seasons, cooling of the ocean surface leads to deepening of the mixed layer - entrainment - and heating of the ocean surface leads to shallowing of it - detrainment. Note that these cooling and heating processes constitute the surface buoyancy forcing. The entrainment and detrainment are estimated from the turbulent kinetic energy in the mixed layer.

Vertical mixing and the KPP in HYCOM

Since the physics are fundamentally different in the boundary surface layer and in the interior ocean, using the same scheme to model the mixing processes in these two domains would lead to a bad simulation. So ocean vertical requires two distinct parameterizations: one for the ocean interior and one for the ocean surface boundary layer. The K-profile-parameterization is particularly attractive because it calculates a diffusivity profile from the bottom to the surface of the ocean. The diffusivity near the surface boundary layer is computed in order to fit the turbulence theory; for the deep ocean, diffusivities for the internal waves, for the shear instability and for the double-diffusion (heat and salt diffusion) are calculated as respectively constant, function of a gradient Richardson number (a measure of the relative importance of stratification to destabilizing shear), and function of the double-diffusion density ratio R_p . At the boundary layer base, boundary layer diffusivity profiles are smoothly matched to interior diffusivity profiles resulting from the processes listed above. The turbulent, boundary layer depth is diagnosed first (it is the maximum depth to which boundary layer eddies can penetrate) and interior diffusivity profiles are combined.

Actually, HYCOM contains 2 mixed layer models, a Kraus-Turner scheme model similar to that implemented in MICOM, and a KPP mixed layer model. The version of HYCOM used in this study includes the KPP, described by (W. G. Large & Doney, 1994).

Chapter 2

The Ecosystem Model

Before dealing with the technical part of the work, we should have a rather succinct overview of the ecosystem model used here, in order to introduce the variables that will be visualized in the results part.

2.1 Description

The ecosystem model used here is an 11-compartments model based on the one-dimensional seven-compartments nitrogen-based model developed by (Fasham, Ducklow, & McKelvie, 1990), but with the nomenclature and modifications given by (Fasham, Sarmiento, Slater, Ducklow, & Williams, 1993) and with the three dimensional extensions described in (Sarmiento et al., 1993). One can split the ecosystem into 2 parts, one concerning the ecosystem evolution in the *euphotic zone*, and one concerning the description of the biochemical tracers below the euphotic zone.

The euphotic zone is the illuminated zone in which light intensities are sufficient for photosynthetic primary production to lead to net growth of phytoplankton. In general, this zone can be up to 200m deep in clear waters of the open ocean, decreasing to about 40m over continental shelves and to as little as 15m in some coastal waters. In practice in this model, the euphotic zone is a layer in the upper part of the ocean which keeps 90 percents of the sun's energy.

Actually only the euphotic zone is modeled; below the euphotic zone, the organic matter is gradually turned over to ammonium, and then to nitrate. The 11-compartments model described in this study models the exchange of nitrogen between the compartments in the euphotic zone. Indeed, the availability of nutrients is a crucial constraint for the development of the biota, while carbon, a fundamental requirement for the support of life on the whole earth, is part of the eight most abundant dissolved elements in ocean and is not considered to be a limiting factor in biological production. The 11 compartments in the model and the different interactions between them are given in figure 2.3.3.

2.2 An overview of the biological cycle

Phytoplankton consists of plant cells ranging in size from 1 to a few hundred microns which drift in the euphotic zone and photosynthesize carbohydrates from carbon dioxide and water. Phytoplankton form the base of oceanic food chains and nutrients move along the chains as grazing and predation take place. Zooplankton feeds on phytoplankton, bacteria and detritus; the nutrients return to solution by excretion and microbial breakdown of Particulate Organic Matter, in other words detritus, and this process is called re-mineralization. Particulate Organic Matter is a result of zooplankton grazing and is converted to Dissolved Organic Matter or sinks vertically in the water column. The euphotic zone is continually being depleted of nutrients, and photosynthetic primary production would be inhibited without vertical mixing, or vertical advection of nutrient-rich water from greater depths.

2.3 The equations for the different tracers in the Euphotic Zone

The concentration units used for the model compartments are $mmol-Nm^{-3}$ for the nitrogen compartments (P, Z, B, NO_3^- , NH_4^+ , DON and PON), $mmol-Cm^{-3}$ for the carbon compartments (DIC, DOC and POC) and $meqm^{-3}$ for the total alkalinity (ALK).

2.3.1 The phytoplankton equation

The phytoplankton organisms evolve according to the equation:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = (1 - \gamma)J(t, z)(N_{\text{nit}} + N_{\text{amm}})P - G_P - \mu_1 \frac{P^2}{k_5 + P} \quad (2.1)$$

Where γ is the fraction of primary production of phytoplankton that is exuded as dissolved organic nitrogen, J is the light limited growth rate, N_{nit} and N_{amm} are the nutrient limitation factors w.r.t. nitrate and ammonium, G_P is the loss of phytoplankton due to zooplankton grazing, and μ_1 and k_5 are the specific mortality rate of phytoplankton and the half-saturation constant for phytoplankton mortality. The first term of equation (2.1) shows that phytoplankton organisms grow if the water is illuminated and contain ammonium and/or nitrate. The second term takes into account the phytoplankton loss because of zooplankton grazing, and the third term the mortality loss. The factors N_{nit} and N_{amm} are defined as:

$$N_{\text{nit}} = \frac{N_n \exp(-\psi N_r)}{k_1 + N_n}, \quad \text{and} \quad N_{\text{amm}} = \frac{N_r}{k_2 + N_r}. \quad (2.2)$$

Here k_1 and k_2 are the half-saturation constants for nitrate and ammonium uptake, and ψ is a constant that parameterizes that planktonic organisms tend to prefer ammonium over nitrate.

2.3.2 The light limited growth rate for phytoplankton

This section explains how the light limited growth rate is computed in this ecosystem model. I found it relevant to include this section here, since the major problems I got had their sources in the routine which computes the light limited growth rate for phytoplankton. Moreover, this is one of the most important issues when modeling the ecosystem.

The light limited growth rate averaged over biochemical layer k of thickness h_k can be put in the form

$$J = \frac{1}{h_k} \int_{d_k}^{d_{k+1}} \frac{V_p \alpha Q_{\text{PAR},z}}{(V_p^2 + \alpha^2 Q_{\text{PAR},z}^2)^{1/2}} dz, \quad (2.3)$$

with d_k and d_{k+1} being the upper and lower interfaces of layer k , V_p being the maximum phytoplankton growth rate, α the initial slope of the photosynthesis-irradiance curve, and $Q_{\text{PAR},z}$ the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR) at depth z . The photosynthetically active radiation at depth z depends on the spectral composition of the light, and the self-shading effect of phytoplankton. The spectral model can be approximated by splitting the euphotic zone into three intervals with boundaries at 5 and 23 m depths. For each interval i , PAR decreases exponentially with a total vertical attenuation coefficient $k_{\text{PAR},i}$ in the form

$$k_{\text{PAR},i} = k_{0,i} + \sum_{j=1}^5 k_{j,i} c^j; i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (2.4)$$

Here $k_{0,i}$ is the light attenuation coefficient for open ocean waters, and the product $\sum_{j=1}^5 k_{j,i} c^j$ takes into account the presence of phytoplankton pigments in the water column. The $k_{j,i}$'s are constants and c is the square root of the pigment (or chlorophyll) concentration C (the latter in $mg\text{-}Chlm^{-3}$). The pigment concentration in $mg\text{-}Chlm^{-3}$ is usually assumed to be linearly related to the phytoplankton concentration in $mmol\text{-}Nm^{-3}$.

2.3.3 The Nitrate equation

The change in the concentration of nitrate due to biochemical processes is caused by the uptake of nitrate by phytoplankton:

$$\frac{\partial \text{NO}_3^-}{\partial t} = -J(t, z) N_{\text{nit}} P. \quad (2.5)$$

Figure 2.1: The ecosystem model used in the euphotic zone, with all of the inter-compartment flows. All the notations are described in appendix B.

Chapter 3

Coupling the Ecosystem model with HYCOM

This chapter first sets the issues of coupling the ecosystem with HYCOM, and then after presenting the different steps that were carried out in the project, draws an outcome of this training period.

3.1 Issues of coupling the Ecosystem

3.1.1 In MICOM

The ecosystem model used here has already been coupled to MICOM. In this case, there are some difficulties coupling the physical and the biochemical models. Indeed, an ecosystem model and a physical model cannot be treated with the same vertical resolution. On the one hand, a physical model is expected to solve the dynamical field from the bottom ocean to the surface; on the other hand the photosynthetically active biota develops in the upper 50–100m of the water column. When we consider MICOM—with the first layer which is the mixed layer and then isopycnic layers—it is clear that the vertical resolution in the upper part of the ocean will not be sufficient to deal with the biota. Hence to couple the two models, physical layers (and particularly the mixed layer) are splitted in order to increase the number of vertical layers in the euphotic zone. Of course the division of the physical layers must be done without increasing dramatically the run-time of the model, that is to say by splitting the physical layers when it is called for by the biota and only there.

Special routines deal with the splitting of the physical layers: in the case of a thick mixed layer, (relative to the euphotic zone), four of the biochemical layers are placed in the euphotic zone and a fifth layer covers the rest of the mixed layer. If a physical layer below the mixed layer becomes thicker than 12m and is positioned in the euphotic zone, the physical layer is splitted into two (or more) biochemical sublayers.

3.1.2 In HYCOM

When we consider coupling the ecosystem with the physical model HYCOM, things are much simpler: due to the discretization used in HYCOM, the upper part of the ocean, discretized in z -levels, has a better resolution than in MICOM since the mixed-layer in MICOM is now splitted into several z -levels. Therefore the biological equations can be solved directly on HYCOM layers without any need to split them, and the convection, diffusion, and advection of the biological tracers can be done using the routines already applied for temperature and salinity in HYCOM.

3.2 The different steps for coupling the ecosystem

The different steps that have been passed during the training period at the Nansen Center are now presented.

3.2.1 Getting started

Starting to work in a completely new environment and in a new scientific field, made it necessary to start the project with an intense literature study to become familiar with the model systems to be used and the underlying oceanography and ecosystem biology.

To work on the project, a Unix station and all the scientific articles I could need were at my disposal. I was also given access to a Cray Origin 2000 super computer with 128 processors for compiling and running the model.

Before even starting getting more familiar with the codes of HYCOM, I first had to get more familiar with a new programming language: indeed, the HYCOM sub-routines are written in a combination of Fortran 77 and Fortran 90.

3.2.2 Dealing with the codes

The first step for coupling the physical and the ecosystem models in HYCOM was to include a single tracer in the physical code; in this manner, it is submitted to convection, advection, and diffusion. Then the conservation of this tracer in each conservative routine where it was modified was checked. After making sure that the single tracer was conserved, the 11 biological tracers were included by following the same procedure as with a single tracer.

Then the ecosystem model was dealt with. The codes available for the ecosystem were adapted to MICOM. The equations were already discretized, but implemented on MICOM vertical discretization and it was necessary to implement everything on HYCOM vertical discretization. Some routines used for MICOM could merely be suppressed when coupling the ecosystem with HYCOM: the routines dealing with the convection and the diffusion of the biological tracers were not needed anymore

since these processes are directly computed within the physical routines in HYCOM.

After the compiling and debugging of the the model, the model was run on a rather coarse resolution to check the consistency of the results; an already spun up physical model was used, and the ecosystem run for 3 years.

The examination of the results was the last part of the training period. Which were the most relevant plots to look at, and whether they allowed to validate the work done was one of the principle issues of this stage.

3.2.3 First results, and problem

The mixed layer deepens in winter and shallows in summer. The shallowing of the mixed layer in spring takes place with a phytoplankton bloom, starting at the equator and propagating northwards.

When visualizing the first results after 3 years of integration, the phytoplankton did not act as expected.

When checked, the initial conditions for the concentration of nitrate were correct.

First it could have been assumed that the model needs to run for a while to get into the right cycle, but actually, even when running the model for several years, things didn't improve.

However, zooplankton followed the same behaviour as phytoplankton with a gap of approximately 2 weeks and therefore behaved as expected. Hence, the conclusion could be drawn that there was something wrong with the computation of the phytoplankton evolution. Focusing on the routine computing the phytoplankton growing rate—this routine was rather new (adapted to HYCOM) and had not been tested yet—some errors were eventually detected in it, the most important one being a dimensional error. After correcting it, the results were far better and the phytoplankton bloom started at a reasonable time, and lasted for a reasonable time too. These results are presented and discussed in chapter 4. They aim at showing the general behaviour of some variables such as nitrate and phytoplankton and can validate the work that has been done here. However these results can only provide a qualitative approach and with the time left, a so-called twin-experiment was run. That's the topic of the next section.

3.2.4 Twin-experiment and another problem

A twin-experiment was run, that is to say running MICOM and HYCOM without including the ecosystem both for 10 years in order to spin them up with the same initial conditions and forcing fields, and then after including the ecosystem running them for 3 more years. This allows to compare the models quantitatively, and we can then try to find out some sources of the differences.

Moreover trying to run HYCOM with the ecosystem helped us identifying something else that should be improved in the routine computing the phytoplankton growing rate. With this other configuration, the model that run for the previous experiment

crashed after a few time steps of integration. After testing the model, another failure was pointed out in the routine computing the phytoplankton growth rate. This failure caused the phytoplankton growth rate to become infinite at some grid points, and a test statement controlling the maximum layer thickness where the phytoplankton growth rate is computed solved the problem. This problem was not detected in the previous experiment. It should be noted that in the first experiment with HYCOM, the number of layers was set to 22, and that in the twin-experiment it was set to 17, in agreement with the number used in the version of MICOM. Therefore some layer thicknesses increased and caused the failure to be detectable. Some results are discussed in chapter 4, but this is clearly a study that should be carried on with new applications of the model system and proper validation with observed data.

Chapter 4

Results

The numerical results were converted to and visualized by the software Tecplot (<http://www.amtec.com>).

4.1 Results of the first experiment

The results presented here are only preliminary results, that is to say they can help us showing the consistency of the coupled model, but in-depth analysis of the simulated fields is not possible. Therefore, the analysis will be limited in this section to a qualitative comparison with similar fields obtained with MICOM (see appendix C).

4.1.1 Nitrate

As it has been pointed out in section 2.1, the nitrate is fundamental for the development of the marine biota, therefore it is rather natural to present the simulated nitrate fields first. Nitrate is extracted from surface water during photosynthesis, being converted into organic material. Hence, nitrate becomes partially or totally depleted in surface waters where biological production is high, especially in spring at high latitudes. In figure 4.1, it is seen that for the months April, June and July the concentration of nitrate decreases rapidly as a consequence of photosynthesis.

We notice that the decreasing concentration of nitrate starts at low latitudes and progresses northwards, propagating to higher latitudes; this is expected since phytoplankton needs light (and nitrate) to grow.

In September, nitrate increases again as a result of the deepening of the mixed layer. So the nitrate behaviour is coherent with our knowledge.

4.1.2 Phytoplankton

The northern part of the Atlantic ocean has a deep mixed layer in winter, but experiences a rapid shallowing of the layer in early spring. Therefore, the mixed layer is rich in nutrients in early spring, with low concentrations of biological compartments including phytoplankton. This situation gives birth to a phytoplankton bloom in spring and the simulated fields in figure 4.2 are in accordance with this de-

scription. Moreover, we can clearly see the northwards propagation of the bloom for the months March, April, May and June. At the end of August, the phytoplankton bloom is finished due to the depletion of nitrate in the surface waters. The section plot on figure 4.5 is another illustration of the major features of the phytoplankton bloom. The location of the section is given in figure 4.4. Again the northwards propagation of the phytoplankton bloom is seen (the i -index used being oriented from North to South).

4.1.3 Partial Pressure of CO₂

Another variable that we can look at to check the general behaviour of the model is the partial pressure of CO₂. Here the difference between the partial pressure of CO₂ in the water ($p\text{CO}_{2,w}$) and the partial pressure of CO₂ in the atmosphere ($p\text{CO}_{2,a}$) is plotted. The partial pressure of CO₂ in the water is highly influenced by temperature; when the latter increases, so does the pressure of CO₂ in water. This explains why the average of $\Delta p = p\text{CO}_{2,w} - p\text{CO}_{2,a}$ should be positive in the southern and northern part of the Atlantic, while negative in the northern part. Two major factors influence Δp : temperature and photosynthetic fixation of dissolved inorganic carbon. First, during the spring bloom and the massive photosynthesis in the Northern part, CO₂ is removed from the water and therefore Δp tends to decrease, and is mostly negative in the northern hemisphere. We can see this decrease by looking at February and May in figure 4.3. However, the temperature increases during the warmer seasons and dictates Δp to increase. From figure 4.3 we see that in August, the temperature effect has already overcome the photosynthetic effect and that Δp has increased in the Northern part of the Atlantic, being even mostly positive.

As a conclusion, these first results help validating the coupling that has been realized here, since they are in accordance with the expected behaviour of nitrate, phytoplankton and partial pressure of CO₂.

4.2 Results of the twin-experiment

Some remarks are made here about a few results from the twin-experiment. The study that has been done in this last part only gives some hints about differences that can be found between MICOM and HYCOM coupled with the ecosystem. It is expected that in-depth study of the differences can be built on the results presented here.

To plot the numerical time series, a point of the grid is chosen at 30°N and 33°W, and annual cycles are represented.

First of all, figure 4.6 gives the evolution of the mixed layer depth in MICOM and HYCOM. It is hard to compare the mixed layer depths quantitatively because in HYCOM the mixed layer depth is diagnosed whereas in MICOM it is a prognostic variable. Therefore these quantities are not directly comparable. The mixed layer depth in HYCOM is diagnosed by considering the depth where the density from the surface increases by 0.2kg.m^{-3} . Figures 4.7 and 4.8 indicate that the evolution of

the mixed layers is highly correlated to the evolution of nitrate and phytoplankton concentrations. For HYCOM, when the mixed layer depth starts to decrease in March, the concentration of nitrate follows, and in the same time the phytoplankton concentration starts to increase. Indeed, during winter, the mixed layer is deep and therefore carries an important quantity of nitrate, and in early spring when the mixed layer shallows the concentration of nitrate in the mixed layer is high which is one of the requested conditions for phytoplankton grow. Therefore during the warmer seasons we notice a higher concentration of phytoplankton and a lower concentration of nitrate. Similarly, in September, the depth of the mixed layer starts to increase and so does the nitrate concentration, while the phytoplankton concentration decreases.

Secondly, figure 4.8 and figure 4.7 clearly indicate that nitrate concentration in the mixed layer is higher in HYCOM and that phytoplankton concentration gets higher as well during the spring bloom (the concentrations for HYCOM given here are averaged values in the mixed layer). We would like to hypotize that the computation of the vertical mixing is one possible source for this difference. Due to the KPP scheme used in HYCOM (see section 1.3.3), the vertical mixing should be stronger than in MICOM which uses a Kraus-Turner scheme (see section 1.3.3) and we assume that this explains the differences noticed. This statement is based on Fick's law that states that vertical concentration gradients tend to decrease with vertical mixing. This explains the higher concentration of nitrate at the surface since nitrate has, in general, a positiv concentration gradient (with respect to the depth) most time of the year. However, phytoplankton has a negativ concentration gradient, therefore we would expect a lower concentration at the surface in HYCOM. This turns out to be the case before the onset of the spring bloom. When the spring bloom starts, the effect of the phytoplankton growth rate is orders of magnitude stronger than changes in the vertical mixing, and the availability of nitrate in the mixed layer determines the evolution of the bloom. Hence, the higher nitrate concentration in HYCOM explains the higher phytoplankton concentration during the spring bloom. However the hypothesis of a stronger vertical mixing in HYCOM has to be checked, and it could be done for instance by comparing the vertical fluxes of biological compartments.

It is interesting to note that, although the phytoplankton growth rate depends on temperature (it increases with the temperature), temperature has probably no consistent influence on the difference between the concentrations in MICOM and in HYCOM. Indeed, figure 4.9 shows that the simulated temperature of the two models are quite similar.

Finally, the two section plots in figure 4.10 and figure 4.11 show that the vertical resolution in HYCOM is far better than the resolution in MICOM. That's why we would like to trust HYCOM results more than MICOM results. However, this statement is probably precocious for the momemt and we have to be careful: MICOM has been developed and tested for a decade now, and has been validated, whereas HYCOM is new and has yet to be tested. Therefore, HYCOM could be more

trustable, but this remains to be verified.

(a) End of February

(b) End of May

(c) End of June

(d) End of July

(e) End of September

Figure 4.1: Concentration of nitrate ($mmol.m^{-3}$) (note the quasi exponential contour intervals)

(a) End of February

(b) End of March

(c) End of April

(d) End of May

(e) End of June

(f) End of August

Figure 4.2: Concentration of phytoplankton ($mmol.m^{-3}$) (note the quasi exponential contour intervals)

(a) End of February

(b) End of May

(c) End of August

Figure 4.3: $\Delta p(ppm)$

Figure 4.4: The section used in the section plots that follow is represented here.

(a) End of February

(b) End of March

(c) End of April

(d) End of May

(e) End of June

(f) End of August

Figure 4.5: Concentration of phytoplankton in a section ($mmol.m^{-3}$) (note the quasi exponential contour intervals)

Figure 4.6: Annual cycle of the mixed layer depth (m)

Figure 4.7: Annual cycle of the concentration of nitrate in the mixed layer ($mmol.m^{-3}$)

Figure 4.8: Annual cycle of the concentration of phytoplankton in the mixed layer ($mmol.m^{-3}$)

Figure 4.9: Annual cycle of the temperature

Figure 4.10: MICOM: Concentration of phytoplankton in a section in March (mmol.m^{-3})

Figure 4.11: HYCOM: Concentration of phytoplankton in a section in March (mmol.m^{-3})

Conclusion

The aim of the work presented here was to couple an ocean general circulation model HYCOM, that is isopycnal in its basis and applies z levels in the upper part, with an 11-compartments model for the ecosystem. Therefore, after a succinct theoretical presentation of both models, the technical steps to reach the coupling have been described in order to show the problems that were encountered and the issues of the project. The results obtained after running this version of the model are discussed. While observing the becoming of biological compartments during the third year of integration, we can draw the conclusion that the coupling has been achieved and the aim has been reached.

We would like to trust HYCOM simulated fields more than those of another isopycnic coordinate ecosystem-coupled model MICOM, since we have seen that the vertical resolution in the upper part of the ocean where the biota mostly grow is far better in HYCOM.

Properly comparing the newly ecosystem-coupled model with the coupled version of MICOM would be very interesting as a further study. This was actually the purpose of leading the last experiment of the training period, the twin-experiment (both models were ran with the most similar parameters, forcing fields and initial conditions as possible) but the time frame of the training period made it only a small beginning in the process of comparing the models.

The models should first of all be ran on a horizontal grid with higher resolution in order to precise the marine biota behaviour in the horizontal. All the biological compartments should be detailed in a further study and numerical times series exploited on several grid points. The vertical mixing is computed differently in MICOM and HYCOM since the former uses a Kraus-Turner scheme and the latter uses a KPP parameterisation, and it would be interesting to precise the influence of this difference on the ecosystem, because the vertical movements of the biological tracers plays an important role in the development of the biota. Actually, it has been shown here that the nitrate concentration is higher with HYCOM than with MICOM which leads to a higher phytoplankton concentration during spring bloom, and it has been assumed that a stronger vertical mixing in HYCOM could explain that. To prove or refuse this assumption, a further work could be to compute the vertical fluxes of biological compartments to compare them in both models.

Appendix A

Barotropic and Baroclinic equations used in MICOM and HYCOM

Barotropic continuity equation The barotropic continuity equation reads

$$\frac{\partial p'_{bot}\eta}{\partial t_\alpha} + \nabla_\alpha \cdot (\bar{v}p'_{bot}),$$

where $p'_{bot}\eta$ is the barotropic pressure at the bottom of the ocean and is supposed to be time-independent.

Barotropic momentum equation The barotropic momentum equation reads

$$\frac{\partial \bar{v}}{\partial t} + f\vec{k} \wedge \bar{v} = -\alpha_0 \nabla(p'_{bot}\eta) + \frac{\partial \bar{v}^*}{\partial t}.$$

The term $\alpha_0 \nabla(p'_{bot}\eta)$ can be interpreted as an approximation to the vertical average of ∇M with α_0 a representative value of α . The last term represents the errors in the vertical average of the momentum equation, made when neglecting contributions from nonlinear terms etc.

Baroclinic continuity equation The baroclinic continuity equation is discretized in α and becomes simply

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t_\alpha} \Delta p' + \nabla_\alpha \cdot (\bar{v} \Delta p') = \frac{\Delta p'}{p'_{bot}} \nabla_\alpha \cdot (p'_{bot} \bar{v}).$$

Baroclinic momentum equation The baroclinic momentum equation reads

$$\frac{\partial v'}{\partial t_\alpha} + \bar{v} \nabla_\alpha \bar{v} + f\vec{k} \wedge \bar{v}' = -\nabla_\alpha M' - \frac{\partial \bar{v}^*}{\partial t_\alpha},$$

with

$$M'(x, y, \alpha, t) = M(x, y, \alpha, t) - \alpha_0 p'_{bot}(x, y) \eta(x, y, t)$$

Appendix B

The equations for the Ecosystem

The concentration units used for the model compartments are $mmol - Nm^{-3}$ for the nitrogen compartments (P, Z, B, NO_3^- , NH_4^+ , DON and PON), $mmol - Cm^{-3}$ for the carbon compartments (DIC, DOC and POC) and $meqm^{-3}$ for the total alkalinity (ALK).

The phytoplankton equation The phytoplankton organisms evolve according to the equation:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial t} = (1 - \gamma)J(t, z)(N_{nit} + N_{amm})P - G_P - \mu_1 \frac{P^2}{k_5 + P}$$

Where γ is the fraction of primary production of phytoplankton that is exuded as dissolved organic nitrogen, J is the light limited growth rate, N_{nit} and N_{amm} are the nutrient limitation factors w.r.t. nitrate and ammonium, G_P is the loss of phytoplankton due to zooplankton grazing, and μ_1 and k_5 are the specific mortality rate of phytoplankton and the half-saturation constant for phytoplankton mortality.

The zooplankton equation Zooplankton's concentration is modelled as

$$\frac{\partial Z}{\partial t} = \beta_P G_P + \beta_B G_B + \beta_{POM} G_{PON} - f_{DON} - \mu_2 \frac{Z^2}{k_6 + Z},$$

with μ_2 the maximum Zooplankton loss rate (excretory and mortality losses), k_6 the half-saturation constant for the loss rate, G_P , G_B , and G_{PON} and the corresponding β -quantities the grazing rates and the assimilation efficiencies of zooplankton on phytoplankton, bacteria and particulate organic matter., and with f_{DON} the change in DON pool.

The bacteria equation Bacteria concentration evolves according to the following equation:

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} = f_{B,DON} + f_{B,NH_4^+} - \mu_3 B - G_B$$

Where μ_3 is the bacterial excretion rate, and G_B is the grazing rate of zooplankton on bacteria. Hence, the third and fourth term of this equation represent respectively

the loss of bacteria due to excretion and grazing of zooplankton.

Finally f_{B,NH_4^+} and $f_{B,DON}$ are the flows of nitrogen from the ammonium and DON pools) to the bacteria compartment.

Nitrate The change in the concentration of nitrate due to biochemical processes is caused by the uptake of nitrate by phytoplankton:

$$\frac{\partial NO_3^-}{\partial t} = -J(t, z)N_{nit}P.$$

Ammonium Ammonium is taken up by phytoplankton and bacteria (as it is shown by the first two terms of the following equation) and is gained from bacteria and zooplankton through excretory losses (see the last two terms of equation the following equation):

$$\frac{\partial NH_4^+}{\partial t} = -J(t, z)N_{amm}P - f_{B,NH_4^+} + \mu_3B + \varepsilon\mu_2\frac{Z^2}{k_6 + Z}.$$

Particulate Organic Matter (POM) A more common term for POM is detritus: it comes from the the dead phytoplankton and from the zooplankton grazing on the phytoplankton, the bacteria and the POM pools. The equations for, respectively the Particulate Organic Nitrogen (PON) and the Particulate Organic Carbon (POC) read:

$$\frac{\partial PON}{\partial t} = (1 - \beta_1)G_P + (1 - \beta_2)G_B - \beta_3G_{PON} + \mu_1\frac{P^2}{k_5 + P} - \mu_4PON - w\frac{\partial PON}{\partial z},$$

and

$$\frac{\partial POC}{\partial t} = (1 - \beta_1)G_P R_P + (1 - \beta_2)G_B R_B - \beta_3G_{POC} + \mu_1\frac{P^2}{k_5 + P}R_P - \mu_4POC - w\frac{\partial POC}{\partial z}.$$

with μ_4 the specific rate of breakdown of detritus to DON and w the sinking velocity of detritus. A fraction of the detritus pool is converted to Dissolved Organic Matter (DOM) and a fraction sinks vertically in the water column.

Dissolved Organic Matter (DOM) The biogenic sinks and sources for the total alkalinity equations read

$$\frac{\partial A_T}{\partial t} = -\frac{\partial N_n}{\partial t} - 2\frac{\partial CaCO_3}{\partial t}.$$

Appendix C

Results with MICOM

Here are some plots obtained with the ecosystem coupled with MICOM, that shows the phytoplankton bloom, the evolution of the nitrate, and of the $\Delta p\text{CO}_2 = p\text{CO}_{2,w} - p\text{CO}_{2,a}$.

(a) End of February

(b) End of May

(c) End of June

(d) End of July

(e) End of October

Figure C.1: Concentration of nitrate ($mmol.m^{-3}$) (quasi exponential contours in intervals)

(a) End of February

(b) End of Mars

(c) End of April

(d) End of May

(e) End of June

(f) End of August

Figure C.2: Concentration of Phytoplankton ($mmol.m^{-3}$) (quasi exponential contour intervals)

(a) End of February

(b) End of May

(c) End of July

Figure C.3: $\Delta P(ppm)$

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